

**Edited by
Vladan Pantović
Dušan Starčević**

INFOTECH

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Infotech 2025
Proceedings**

Arandjelovac, June 4-5, 2025

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INFOTECH 2025

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Edited by

Vladan Pantović

Dušan Starčević

Arandjelovac, 4 – 5, June, 2025

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INFOTECH 2025

Arandjelovac, 4 – 5, June, 2025

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Telecommunications and New Media of Serbia**

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P R E F A C E

This year marks the 40th edition of INFOTECH, a regular annual international scientific and professional conference in the field of the development and application of information technologies.

INFOTECH has always followed trends in the development of information and communication technologies, and this year is no different; the obvious dominant theme, addressed in more than half of the papers, is the application of artificial intelligence (AI). Due to the importance of this current topic, a special AI Panel, AI Workshop and AI Keynote were organized.

A total of 23 accepted papers by 58 authors are published in the Proceedings. They are classified according to their subject matter into four sections: Artificial Intelligence, Information Security, Information Technology and Applications, and Management and Information Systems. The tradition continues, and this year INFOTECH also featured authors from abroad (Italy, Canada, United Kingdom, Germany and Bosnia and Herzegovina).

ASIT - the Association for Computing, Informatics, Telecommunications and New Media of Serbia, the organizer of the conference, on the occasion of the important jubilee, published, in cooperation with the Co-Publisher the "Faculty of Project and Innovation Management prof. dr Petar Jovanović", two additional special editions edited by prof. dr Vladan Pantović and prof. emeritus dr Dušan Starčević:

- INFOTECH 2020 – 2024 Selected Papers
- INFOTECH 1995 – 2000 Proceedings: Digital version the classic printed proceedings

We would like to thank everyone who actively participated in the preparation of the INFOTECH 2025 conference, and we expect good cooperation in the coming years as well.

Chairman of the Organizing Board

Nikola Mirković

Chairman of the Scientific Program Board

Prof. dr Vladan Pantović

ENHANCING LITERATURE REVIEWS A TOOL FOR DISCOVERY AND ANALYSIS

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Abstract: *This paper introduces a custom-built Literature Review Tool designed to discover, extract, and rank relevant content from a diverse range of online sources using advanced web scraping and contextual full-text search techniques. The tool enhances the efficiency and accuracy of literature reviews by enabling comprehensive analysis of both scientific publications and grey literature, including blogs, informal reports, and government documents. The paper presents an overview of the tool's core functionalities, including source discovery, article extraction, and content analysis.*

Keywords: *Web scraping and content extraction, full-text search, relevance scoring and highlighting, literature analysis, grey literature.*

1. INTRODUCTION

The surveying, discovery, and systematization of relevant grey literature materials “produced on all levels of government, academics, business and industry in print and electronic formats, [...] which is not controlled by commercial publishers” [1] – such as technical reports, project reports, working papers, white papers, government documents, and other forms – is highly significant [2] for mapping the state of the art with a more balanced view [3], particularly in applied research and innovation, yet it is largely overlooked or unsupported by major academic search engines and structured content repositories, such as Scopus, Lens, ScienceDirect, and Web of Science.

In the absence of efficient tools or structured registries, literature reviews of this kind often rely on either manual web searching or interaction with LLM-based interfaces (such as OpenAI ChatGPT [4]). However, these approaches remain highly unreliable for tasks that demand deterministic responses and fully accurate, complete results, due to issues such as hallucinations or confabulations [5] and inherent biases [6].

Manual web searches are effective for relatively simple tasks, such as gathering information on straightforward, narrowly focused topics or addressing specific problems

with widely accepted answers and minimal conflicting viewpoints. The limitations of manual searching become evident when conducting extensive and systematic grey literature reviews, especially those that require diverse sources, multiple perspectives, and cover different time periods. Manual searching in such cases is time-consuming and labor-intensive, often necessitating a well-coordinated team, thorough planning, and systematization of results.

Even when relevant documents are found, the outcomes of manual searches often fail to justify the time and effort invested. This is especially true when results, despite being well-documented and structured, are not stored in databases that support complex evaluations, aggregations, and analyses. While ad-hoc scripts may assist with some preliminary tasks, they only partially address the challenge of assembling a relevant corpus. Significant additional effort is still required to thoroughly read through these documents and select the most relevant ones.

Among all these activities, only two truly require human effort: defining search queries and reading the discovered articles. Everything else can be automated, including ranked searches across the internet for websites and within websites for articles, scraping article content, storing data in structured, queryable database, and visualizing, filtering, aggregating scores, and ordering the data. Even the manual tasks can be optimized: search queries can be prioritized based on the scores of retrieved results, and reading can be minimized by using contextual full-text search to highlight only the most relevant paragraphs and keywords within the extracted article contents.

This article describes a tool for automated literature discovery and review designed to address key challenges in the field. Developed by a dedicated project team, it is actively used in the ongoing FishEUTrust project to explore, discover, and systematize grey literature on several of its core topics and research questions, such as barriers to and drivers of seafood purchasing and consumption behaviour. The tool's development was motivated by the clear absence of any suitable existing solutions at the time (mid-2023).

2. MAIN FEATURES AND WORKFLOW

The Literature Review Tool is designed to overcome the challenges of manual internet article searches by automating the discovery of relevant articles and sections, while also supporting user collaboration during content analysis. The workflow consists of four key stages:

1. Website search which involves searching websites as sources of specific articles. This step is optional, as users can manually provide a set of websites if they already know where to search.
2. Article search on specific websites involves searching for articles within the subset of websites identified in step 1, websites manually entered by the user, or both.
3. Paragraph search within articles takes place after step 2, once articles have been collected and the search is complete. The tool downloads content from the top 4,000 ranked articles, extracts and indexes their content, and enables full-text search on that data.
4. Tagging websites and articles with statuses such as relevant, potentially relevant, or not relevant to helps with collaboration among multiple users. This tagging can be done at any stage in the workflow.

Figure 1. Literature Review Tool workflow

Figure 1 illustrates the possible steps in this workflow, detailing the inputs and outputs for each stage. Discovering websites involves website searching and analysis. The article search is performed on the identified relevant websites to collect material for content extraction. Paragraph search locates relevant sections within documents, reducing the need for reading the full text.

2.1 Discovering Sites

Searching the entire internet for articles on a specific topic is challenging. The vast amount of information often causes search engines to favor higher-ranked sites optimized for search, which may not always be the most relevant. This can narrow the diversity of results. To address this issue, it is necessary to restrict the search to a predefined set of relevant websites.

In some cases, users may already know the specific websites to target for article searches. In other cases, additional websites need to be identified to expand the source pool. This tool conducts website searches by scanning the internet and scraping context paths from the first five pages of search results. Users provide search queries, and each search result is stored as a triplet consisting of site, query, and page.

For analysis and visualization, the flat rows are grouped by site, with scores aggregated by summing individual contributions and queries aggregated into sets. Each appearance of a site on a page contributes

$$\frac{10}{\text{page number}} \quad (1)$$

to the total score of that site.

For example, if a site appears four times on the first page, its score will be 40, and if it appears once on the second page, it will add 5 to the score.

Figure 2. Left column of the site discoverer page with websites and scores

Hovering over the score number, as shown in Figure 2, opens a dropdown list displaying all the queries for which the site appears. Sites can be marked with the following statuses: “rejected” (red), “uncertain” (yellow), and

“accepted” (green). Users can also add custom statuses – for example, Figure 2 shows an additional status, “academic” (pink), used for websites containing academic literature. Once a site is marked as “accepted,” it is automatically queued for article search (see the next chapter), while other statuses remain descriptive and searchable only.

Query score	Query (7)	Number of searched queries
382.09	BARRIERS TO FISH SEAFOOD PURCHASING CONSUMPTION	x
370.12	FISH SEAFOOD CONSUMER PURCHASING CONSUMPTION	x
353.81	DRIVERS OF FISH SEAFOOD PURCHASING CONSUMPTION	x
345.09	SEAFOOD REASON FOR BUYING FACTOR	x
323.96	FISH REASON FOR BUYING FACTOR	x
295.28	PURCHASING OF AQUACULTURE PRODUCTS BARRIERS DRIVERS	x
235.05	FISH SEAFOOD CONSUMER BUYER BEHAVIOUR	x

Figure 3. Right column of the site discoverer page with queries and scores

Since this process involves searching across the entire internet, queries should be longer and more specific to narrow the results. The query score helps guide users in refining their queries. For each query, the score is calculated as the sum of

$$\frac{1}{\text{site rank}} \quad (2)$$

for each site found by that query, where the site with the highest score is assigned rank 1 and subsequent sites receive incrementally higher ranks. This sum is then multiplied by 100.

Queries can be deleted, which also removes all associated results. This action cannot be undone, although users can manually re-enter the same query if needed. Checking the boxes for specific queries filters the websites listed in the left column, showing only those with scores that include the selected queries (see Figure 3). Additionally, users can perform a fuzzy search by site or combine these filters.

2.2 Discovering Articles

After optionally searching for and analyzing websites, and marking some as accepted, the next step is to search for articles. If websites were not previously identified through a search, they must be manually entered, since both websites and queries are required inputs for the article search. This search then looks for articles matching the specified queries on the designated websites.

For the initial search, both a site and a query are required. Subsequent searches allow entering either or both. When a new site is added, all previous queries will be searched on that site. When a new query is added, it will be searched across all previously specified sites. If both a new site and a new query are provided, the new query will be searched across all existing sites, and all previous queries will be searched on the new site. Searches for existing site-query pairs are not repeated. To refresh results, users must remove and re-enter existing entries. This approach ensures consistent scoring and relevant results.

The article scraper extracts article URIs and titles from the top three pages of search results. Each site-query pair triggers three scrapes, one for each page. Limiting extraction to the first three pages has proven sufficient, as the search is focused on specific websites rather than the entire internet, resulting in less bias compared to the site search phase.

The outcome of each search contains: site, query, page, scraped article URI and title. These flat rows are grouped by article, scores are aggregated by summing individual contributions, while queries and sites are combined into sets. Each appearance of a URI on a page contributes

$$\frac{10}{\text{page number}} \quad (3)$$

to the article's total score. For example, an article that appears twice on the first page will have a score of 20, and a score of 5 if it appears once on the second page.

Article score	Article	Site
271.67	Report on consumer aspects related to European organic ...	oraqua.eu
245.00	M18 Submitted to EC - OrAqua	oraqua.eu
240.00	The European research project PrimeFish delivers its first ...	cetmar.org
231.67	Economic Report of the EU Aquaculture sector (STECF-18-19)	stecf.jrc.ec.europa.eu
230.00	The Future of Food from the Sea Ocean Panel	oceanpanel.org
230.00	What do Asian consumers crave in alternative seafood?	gfi-apac.org
228.33	Deliverable D4.1 - OrAqua	oraqua.eu

Figure 4. Left column of the article discoverer page with articles and scores

Hovering over the score number opens a dropdown listing all queries for which the article was found. Like websites, articles can be marked with statuses such as “rejected”

(red), “uncertain” (yellow), and “accepted” (green). Users can also add custom statuses – for example, Figure 4 shows an additional status, “integrated” (light blue), which denotes manually imported articles that were also found by the tool. These statuses are descriptive and can be used to filter articles.

Query score	Number of searched queries	Website score	Number of searched websites
745.44	FISH SEAFOOD PURCHASE	189.84	oraqua.eu
742.93	FISH SEAFOOD PURCHASING	46.53	cetmar.org
723.92	FISH SEAFOOD CONSUMPTION	45.60	oceanpanel.org
707.94	FISH SEAFOOD BUY	38.81	stecf.jrc.ec.europa.eu
666.40	FISH SEAFOOD PREFERENCE	26.97	aquaculture2020.org
656.02	BARRIER TO FISH SEAFOOD PURCHASING CONSUMPTION	26.32	fdrsinc.org
627.22	PERCEPTION OF FISH SEAFOOD	20.30	foodandlandusecoalition.org
625.47	FISH SEAFOOD CONSUMER BUYER BEHAVIOUR	19.93	gfi-apac.org
616.37	REASON FOR BUYING FISH SEAFOOD	18.11	aqua.cl
		17.73	gfi.org
		16.38	primefish.cetmar.org
		15.73	vibarstvo.mps.hr

Figure 5. Right column of the article discoverer page with queries, websites, and scores

Practical use has shown that queries for article searches should be shorter than those for website searches. Because the search is already limited to specific websites, there is less need for highly specific queries.

Queries and sites can be deleted which also removes all associated results. This action cannot be undone, although the same query and/or site can be manually re-entered if necessary. Removing a site found by the tool, removes its “accepted” status from the Website Discoverer page.

Ticking the checkboxes for queries, as shown in Figure 5, filters the results to display only articles with scores that include the selected queries. Selecting checkboxes for sites shows only articles from those sites. Users can also search by title, URL, or content, or combination of these inputs.

2.3 Discovering Paragraphs

Once all relevant websites and search queries for article discovery are entered and the search is completed with all relevant article URIs collected, the retrieval of articles from these URIs can be automated. Their content is then extracted and indexed, enabling full-text search within the retrieved files. This enhances the Article Discoverer’s ability to filter by article content and provides the foundation for paragraph searches, including highlighting matching words and scoring search results.

Paragraph discovery simplifies the article review process by reducing the need to download, open and read entire articles. Identifying a relevant paragraph is often sufficient to extract valuable information or decide if an article is worth further consideration. Additionally, the full-text search functionality offers more capabilities than typical searches supported in HTML, PDF, or DOCX readers.

Figure 6. Left column of the paragraph discoverer page with Paragraphs and Scores

The system searches for articles containing content that matches the provided query, displaying results sorted by full-text search score and article score based on the result page, as shown in Figure 6. Initially, only the first paragraph of each article is retrieved, with an option to load up to 20 additional paragraphs. Matching query terms are highlighted in bold.

Full-text search identifies natural language texts that match the query in a fuzzy manner, ranking and highlighting relevant sections based on their similarity to the query. Indexing article contents generates a sorted list of distinct lexemes – normalized word forms that group different variants of the same term.

Supported query syntax includes:

- Unquoted text searches for lexemes in any order.
- "Quoted text" searches for lexemes in the given order.
- Dash (-) as a prefix excludes that lexeme from results.
- OR acts as the logical operator for combining queries.

Both the Paragraph Discoverer and the content search within the Article Discoverer are built on full-text search. This functionality applies only to successfully downloaded and indexed articles, with up to 4000 of the top-scoring articles (first 400 pages) being downloaded and indexed.

Another advantage of indexing article content is the automatic availability of lexeme frequencies across all

documents. Irrelevant lexemes can be excluded from the frequency table, as shown in Figure 7 below.

Figure 7. Right column of the paragraph discoverer page with lexemes and scores

There are three modes for displaying frequencies: (1) Global – showing frequency across all documents; (2) Search – displaying frequency within documents resulting from a paragraph search; and (3) Document – showing frequency in the currently displayed document on the left.

This feature helps users identify the general theme of a document or collection of documents, inspires the formulation of search queries, and can be used to generate word clouds, among other applications.

3. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

The Literature Review Tool began as a set of simple utility scripts aimed at streamlining the process of searching for and documenting useful links and content from the internet, with minimal complexity and a low learning curve. Over time, it evolved into a more advanced system, with features such as scoring mechanisms, automated content retrieval, and full-text search, significantly reducing the need for manual effort.

Future enhancements aim to expand the tool’s capabilities to include data interpretation. Features currently under development include:

- Multilingual support by language metadata extraction and leveraging relevant dictionaries for advanced

- features such as synonym matching across different lexemes in multiple languages.
- Image extraction from documents and search, like *Images* tab in Google search.
- Results version management for tracking changes across different versions of results.
- Grouping search queries and results by conceptual topics for improved organization and analysis.
- Leveraging found documents, extracted content, queries, and scores as inputs for AI tools such as ChatGPT. AI-generated responses can be stored as supplementary metadata linked to the corresponding documents. While some of these capabilities are currently achievable using external tools – such as RAG (Retrieval-Augmented Generation) frameworks like Quivr – the goal is to provide tighter integration.

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